

Pest resistance—insects

Gall midge (GM) resistance in traditional rice varieties of Manipur

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We tested 21 traditional rice varieties for resistance to GM *Orseolia oryzae*

Wood-Mason, a serious pest of rice in Manipur, in the field at Iroisemba 1986-88. Surekha and TN1 were the resistant and susceptible checks.

Seedlings at 1 mo old were transplanted in four 10-hill rows of each variety at 20- × 15-cm spacing. To ensure adequate pest pressure, TN1 was planted after every 20 rows. Plots were fertilized to induce tillering.

Damage (% silvershoots and % infested hills) was graded 45 d after transplanting.

In pooled 3-yr data, Phouren and Moirangphou khokngangbi show consistent resistance (see table). Akhanphou, Taothabi, Changphai, Kohima phou, Kakchengphou, and Chakhao amubi show less than 5% infestation. □

Reaction of traditional rice cultivars to GM. Iroisemba, Manipur, India, 1986-88.

Variety	1986		1987		1988		Mean		Resistance rating ^a
	Silver-shoots (%)	GM-infested hills (%)							
Moirangphou khokngangbi	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Phouren	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Akhanphou	2	5	1	2	1	2	2	3	3
Chakhao amubi	2	5	2	2	1	2	2	3	3
Changphai	2	5	2	2	2	5	2	4	3
Kakchengphou	2	2	2	5	2	5	2	4	3
Kohima phou	1	2	4	5	2	5	3	4	3
Taothabi	2	5	2	2	1	2	2	3	3
Buman	7	15	6	15	4	10	6	13	5
Langmanphou	4	8	4	8	3	5	3	7	5
Changlei	6	15	6	12	5	10	6	12	5
Chiposelak	8	12	4	10	4	10	5	11	5
Keibuchirong	4	10	3	8	3	5	3	8	5
Moirangphou	3	5	4	8	6	20	4	11	5
Nahazing	8	15	5	12	4	10	6	12	5
Rarangma	4	12	3	8	4	10	4	10	5
Taothabi angouba	10	18	9	10	3	15	7	14	5
Kumbi phou	12	20	15	22	6	12	11	18	7
Sangsangba	10	2	12	28	5	10	9	21	7
Tadukan	7	22	9	25	6	20	7	22	7
Tangangkate	9	25	11	28	7	20	9	24	7
Surekha (resistant check)	2	5	3	5	1	2	2	4	3
TN1 (susceptible check)	16	55	21	74	10	30	16	53	9

^a Based on *Standard evaluation system for rice* scale of 0-9: 0 = no damage, 1 = resistant, 3 = moderately resistant, 5 = moderately susceptible, 7 = susceptible, and 9 = highly susceptible.

Outbreak of blue beetle in India

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Blue beetle *Leptispa pygmaea* Baly. (Chrysomelidae: Coleoptera) has been considered a minor pest of rice, with incidences recorded in parts of Tamil Nadu, South Kanara, Mysore, Cochin, and Malabar District of Kerala.

A serious outbreak occurred in Kuzhithurai Division, Kanyakumari District, Tamil Nadu Nov-Dec 1988 (kumbapoo, or second season). Incidence was very severe on about 50 ha of Ponmani during maximum tillering and panicle initiation.

The rice cultivation tract in Nattalam and Killiyur blocks is locally called Ela, which means low-lying rice area surrounded by hill and forest vegetation. The ricefields are situated in the valley, with coconut, banana, vegetable crops, and forest plantations on both

sides. The area is very fertile and has good irrigation from storage ponds.

We surveyed blue beetle incidence, damage, and life stages during its maximum feeding stage on 40 rice leaves sampled from 40 clumps. The pest in both larval and adult stage was found feeding on the upper surface of rice leaves, causing longitudinal white streaks of scraping. In severe attack, the leaves folded longitudinally and dried up. From a distance, the affected rice patch showed severe drying symptoms resembling that caused by

leaffolder except that there was no webbing and tying of leaf margins.

In certain pockets, the young crop was attacked, resulting in stunting and severe drying symptoms. Incidence was higher in shaded areas.

The adult beetle is dark bluish-green, shiny and metallic, elongated with fine striations or pittings on the elytra. The beetles are very weak flyers

and soft, without hardness. The larva is a soft-bodied, campodeiform grub, pale white with a brown head, and with a sclerotized tubular process at the abdominal tip. The larvae arrange themselves in a longitudinal line on the leaf surface, with about 7/leaf on average (maximum 10-12). Fecal pellets found on the surface of affected leaves are very tiny and powdery.

A larva pupates by attaching itself to the leaf surface by its posterior end. About three pale brown pupae could be seen on each leaf. A large number of white pupal skin are seen on leaf surfaces after beetle emergence.

The simultaneous presence of all stages of the pest indicates overlapping broods. □

New sources of resistance to rice leaffolder (LF)

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We screened 1,430 F₄ progenies of TKM6, Muthumanikam, and Ptb 33 crossed to IR4707-106-3-2 during 1988

Reaction pattern of parents and progenies to LF damage, Laurel, Batangas, Philippines, 1988 wet season. Each pattern indicates reaction at sequential 7-d scoring intervals. R = resistant, I = intermediate, S = susceptible.

wet season in Balakilong, Laurel, Batangas. The progenies had been found resistant in the F₂ and F₃ in greenhouse screening.

Seedlings raised in wet seedbeds were transplanted 21 d after seeding in 2 rows of 25 hills each. Parents and susceptible check IR36 were planted every 100 rows. At 50 d after transplanting (DT), 120 kg N/ha was applied to increase plant lushness that would attract LF adults from adjacent fields.

Plants were scored for plant damage when susceptible check IR36 had more than 50% leaf damage; scoring was repeated every 7 d to harvest.

Damage could not be scored beyond 86 DT, when early-maturing TKM6

progenies had to be harvested. Late-maturing Muthumanikam progenies and Ptb 33 were damaged by a typhoon after the third scoring.

All parents showed resistance to LF at 72 DT. Muthumanikam and Ptb 33 showed intermediate resistance to susceptibility at later stages, almost comparable to the female parent IR4707-106-3-2 and susceptible check IR36 (Fig. 1a). TKM6 progenies had the best resistance (Fig. 1b). Ptb 33 progenies had limited resistance (Fig. 1c). Progenies of both Ptb 33 and Muthumanikam were late-maturing and tended to show intermediate to susceptible reaction to LF at booting. □

Pest resistance—other pests

Analysis of isozymes in rice varieties tolerant of and susceptible to herbicide butachlor

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We examined the relationships of peroxidase and esterase isozymes in indica rice varieties with tolerance for butachlor, to establish a biochemical means of screening for tolerance.

Resistant Wu-Jie-Gu and Long-Jiang-Dao; susceptible Yuan-Feng-Zao, B3, and IR24; and medium-resistant Lu-Hong-Zao 1 were used. Germinated seeds were sown in 5 cm soil in 45- × 25- × 15-cm plastic boxes.

At the 2-3 leaf stage, seedlings were soaked with 100 ppm butachlor solution or water.

At 1-5 d after treatment, electrophoresis was made with 7% polyacrylamide gel system. Peroxidase isozymes were stained with acetate-benzidine and esterase isozymes with 1-naphthyl acetate and fast blue RR salt.

Eleven peroxidase isozymes were separated by electrophoregram (Fig. 1). The tenth isozyme (Rf=0.88) was more active in susceptible varieties than in tolerant or medium varieties treated with butachlor, especially 3 d after treatment. In control, there was no difference between zymograms of tolerant and susceptible varieties.

Six esterase isozymes were identified (Fig. 2). The third isozyme (Rf=0.79)